

Solid-State NMR Structure Determination of a Lipid-Embedded Heptahelical Membrane Protein

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Abstract: Structure determination of integral membrane proteins, especially in their native environment, is a formidable challenge in structural biology. Here we demonstrate that magic angle spinning solid-state NMR can be used to determine structures of membrane proteins reconstituted in synthetic lipids, an environment similar to the natural membrane. We combine a large number of experimentally determined interatomic distances and local torsional restraints to solve the structure of an oligomeric membrane protein of common seven-helical fold, *Anabaena* sensory rhodopsin (ASR). We determined the atomic resolution detail of the oligomerization interface of ASR trimer, and the arrangement of helices, side chains, and the retinal cofactor within the monomer.

Editorial Summary

A solid-state NMR-based strategy for determining the structure of an oligomeric, seven-helix membrane protein (*Anabaena* sensory rhodopsin) in a lipid environment is described.

INTRODUCTION

Membrane proteins comprise about a third of all proteins, but their structures are strongly underrepresented in the Protein Data Bank. X-ray crystallography remains the primary tool for membrane structure determination and major accomplishments have been reported in recent years.^{1,2} Particularly remarkable advances have been achieved in understanding the G-protein coupled receptors.³⁻⁷ The last decade has also witnessed a number of major achievements by NMR spectroscopy. Solution NMR has been successfully used for structure determination of detergent-solubilized membrane proteins,⁸⁻¹⁰ including those with polytopic alpha-helical fold.¹¹⁻¹⁵ Solid-state NMR (SSNMR) has also made seminal contributions into understanding the structure and function of membrane proteins, including ion channels and receptors.¹⁶⁻²⁰ In particular, a structure of chemokine receptor CXCR1 in phospholipid bilayer was determined recently by rotationally aligned NMR using the structure of bovine rhodopsin as a topological template.²¹ Computational approaches that aim to facilitate SSNMR data analysis and to automate structure calculations have also been established.^{22,23}

Here we demonstrate that magic angle spinning (MAS) SSNMR can be used to obtain atomic-resolution structures of multi-spanning helical membrane proteins and their oligomers reconstituted in synthetic lipids. We determined a complete three-dimensional structure of an 81 kDa homotrimer formed by a seven-transmembrane-helical (7TM) protein *Anabaena* Sensory Rhodopsin (ASR) in a model lipid environment, without relying on a pre-existing structural template.

ASR is a microbial retinal-binding photoreceptor that initiates a unique phototransduction cascade involving a soluble transducer, which interacts with DNA and may regulate the expression of several proteins responsible for photosynthesis and circadian clock in cyanobacterium *Anabaena* sp. PCC 7120.^{24,25} A crystal structure of a C-terminally truncated 229-residue ASR has been determined to 2.0 Å resolution.²⁶ We have previously characterized the secondary structure, topology and aggregation state of ASR in lipids,^{27,28} and observed a number of structural differences from the crystal structure. The largest discrepancy is related to the oligomeric state of ASR, which forms bacteriorhodopsin-like symmetric trimers in lipids, in contrast to undulating layers of dimers in crystals.²⁶ Additionally, we observed a short β -hairpin within the B-C loop, which was missing in the crystal structure, and determined that the protein is in a single conformation, while alternate conformations were detected in the crystal structure.²⁶ We also used SSNMR-detected backbone H/D exchange to determine location of the protein in membrane and its light-driven

conformational changes.²⁹ Here, we demonstrate that structure of the entire trimer can be determined in the lipid environment using SSNMR.

RESULTS

Solid-state magic angle spinning NMR

We obtained the atomic resolution structure of ASR by combining torsional and internuclear distance restraints with Paramagnetic Relaxation Enhancement (PRE) constraints determined by MAS SSNMR. ^{13}C - ^{13}C and ^1H - ^1H distance restraints for structure calculation were derived from the measurements on three lipid-reconstituted ASR samples with different patterns of isotope labeling. 2D ^{13}C - ^{13}C Proton Driven Spin Diffusion (PDSD) experiments, 3D Homogeneously Broadened Rotational Resonance spectra (HBR²)³⁰ and 2D ^{13}C -detected proton spin diffusion CHHC experiments³¹ (**Supplementary Table 1**) were collected on sparsely ^{13}C -labeled ASR samples, grown on [1,3- ^{13}C]-glycerol or [2- ^{13}C]-glycerol as carbon sources (denoted as 1,3-ASR and 2-ASR), and regenerated using doubly ^{13}C -labeled retinal (13,20- $^{13}\text{C}_2$). Sparse labeling improved the spectral resolution of the PDSD and CHHC spectra,³² and resulted in numerous well-resolved cross peaks corresponding to medium- and long-range distance restraints (**Fig. 1** and **Supplementary Figs. 1-3**). Sparse labeling was particularly beneficial for improving the resolution of spectra corresponding to the aromatic side chain atoms, and allowed identification of a large number of long-range interhelical correlations, which define the interhelical packing (**Fig. 1a** and **Supplementary Fig. 2b,d**). Additionally, spectrally unambiguous restraints were found between the labeled retinal C13 and C20 carbons and the neighboring residues, defining the core of the monomeric helical bundle (**Fig. 2a** and **Supplementary Fig. 2a,c**).

3D HBR² experiments³⁰ were recorded on 1,3-ASR and 2-ASR, and allowed detection of contacts between the carbonyl and aliphatic atoms with chemical shifts in the range of 15-35 ppm, typically methylene and methyl carbons (**Fig. 1d** and **Supplementary Fig. 1**). Owing to the mainly alpha-helical secondary structure of ASR, the majority of observed HBR² cross peaks corresponded to intra-helical correlations, and helped determine the side chain packing. Notable exceptions are long-range correlations observed within the B-C loop (e.g., G59C'-A71C β , V61C'-I67C γ 2 and V61C'-A68C β), which define the β -hairpin structure, and some interhelical contacts, e.g., W76C'-I113C γ 2.

PRE restraints were collected on a uniformly ^{15}N , ^{13}C -labeled S26C ASR mutant with a covalently attached nitroxide paramagnetic tag.²⁸ PREs constrain interhelical packing between helices A and B of the same monomer,

and provide unambiguous intermolecular distance restraints, defining the oligomerization interface between the neighboring interacting ASR molecules.

Structure determination of trimeric ASR

Chemical shift assignments of ASR have been determined previously (BMRB code 18595). Multidimensional SSNMR spectra of ASR exhibit hundreds of cross peaks (**Fig. 1** and **Supplementary Figs. 1-3**), correlating spatially close pairs of atoms, usually less than 7 Å from one another. However, unambiguously assigning these cross peaks relying solely on the chemical shifts is difficult because of spectral degeneracy. The spectral complexity can be successfully resolved if there is a known structural template. To generate a *de novo* template, we first calculated a low-resolution monomer structure. The information about the intermonomer interface identified from PRE data²⁸ was used to exclude potential internuclear intermonomer distance restraints from the calculation of a monomer fold. To improve convergence of structure calculation at the initial stage, backbone atoms, comprising well-defined α -helices as defined by Chemical Shift Index (CSI) of ASR and by torsion angles extracted using TALOS+ (Torsion Angle Likelihood Obtained from Shift and sequence similarity) (**Supplementary Fig. 4**), were fixed as semi-rigid bodies by introducing hydrogen bonds between the backbone oxygen atom of residue i and the backbone amide proton of residue $i+4$, with the corresponding distances defined in a range of 1.8-2.5 Å. These local restraints were combined with 24 unambiguous intramolecular PRE restraints connecting helices A and B (**Fig. 2a**) and 32 non-redundant internuclear distance restraints defined with the upper limit of 10 Å, which were manually assigned in the 3D HBR² and 2D PDSD spectra (**step 1** of the **Structure Calculation Protocol**, **Fig. 2a** and **Supplementary Table 2**). This set of restraints was subjected to a structure calculation using CNS.³³ Ten lowest energy structures (from 100 calculated) exhibited backbone RMSD of 3.2 Å for the α -helices (**Fig. 2b**), and were selected as a template for further calculations.

In the next step, we separated all cross-peaks into two groups. The first group included correlations that could be ascribed to intra-residue, sequential, short- and medium-range interactions ($|i-j| < 5$). They were temporarily excluded from further consideration. Because of the predominantly helical architecture, the vast majority of the remaining peaks in the second group (corresponding to $|i-j| \geq 5$ correlations) represent inter-helical contacts. This initial classification of long-range cross-peaks ensured rapid conversion of structure calculation, which is demonstrated in **Fig. 2**. The remaining ambiguous long-range cross-peaks and the template were subjected to an iterative structure calculation and cross-peak assignments using ARIA 2.3,³⁴ which identified additional 179 unambiguous long-range restraints (**steps 2 and 3** of the **Structure Calculation Protocol**; **Fig. 2c,e**). In the final step (**step 4** of the **Structure**

Calculation Protocol), the cross peaks from the first group, corresponding to intra-residue, sequential, short- and medium-range interactions were analyzed manually and resulted in additional 1293 intra-residue, 663 sequential, 97 short- ($|i-j|=2$), and 435 medium-range ($|i-j|=3$ or 4) distance restraints. The calculation step using this complete set of intramolecular restraints resulted in an ensemble of 10 structures (out of 100) with the backbone RMSD of 0.6 Å for the α -helices (**Supplementary Fig. 5**). With the knowledge of the monomer structure, we additionally identified five inter-monomer contacts from the PDS spectra (**step 5** of the **Structure Calculation Protocol**), which occur on the interface between helices B and D/E of the adjacent monomers, in agreement with the PRE data (**Fig. 3a**).

For the final structure calculation of a trimer, the distance restraints derived from cross-peaks identified from the HBR² spectra were set to 2.5 - 5.5 Å. PDS cross peaks were converted into distance restraints with upper bounds of 5.5, 6.5, and 7.5 Å for the experiments with mixing times of 100, 250, and 500 ms, respectively. The upper limit for ¹H-¹H distances from the CHHC experiments was set to 5.0 Å, and PRE restraints were converted into distance constraints with an upper bound of 15 Å.³⁵ The final structure calculation performed using CNS resulted in an ensemble of 10 structures (out of 100) with RMSD of 0.8 Å for backbone atoms in the α -helices. The lowest energy trimer structure is shown in **Fig. 3a**. Summary of restraints extracted from spectra, and structural statistics are given in **Supplementary Tables 3-5**.

Structure of ASR trimer

The overall topology of the ASR trimer closely resembles that of its archaeal homolog bacteriorhodopsin (BR) (**Fig. 3a-b**). The oligomerization interface involves helix B in one monomer and helices D and E in the adjacent monomer, and is mainly stabilized by hydrophobic interactions (**Fig. 3a**). Accordingly, all inter-monomer contacts directly identifiable from the NMR spectra are between helices B and D (F42C β -S107C β and W46C ϵ 2-T114C α), and helices B and E (I56C δ 2-V127C γ 1, I56C δ 2-V127C γ 2, L49C α -W131C ϵ 3, and M52C ϵ -C134C β). Some of the key residues involved in the intermonomer packing are conserved or highly similar to those in BR,³⁶ e.g., W131 in ASR and W137 in BR (**Fig. 3c**). However, there is a higher proportion of aromatic residues on the trimerization interface of ASR, for example, F42 and W46 in helix B of ASR replace L48 and I52 of BR (**Fig. 3c**). The higher aromatic content of the oligomerization interface can contribute to the observed high trimer stability of ASR in detergents compared to that of BR.²⁸ Interestingly, the side chain nitrogen of W46 in the SSNMR structure is in a position to form intermolecular hydrogen bond with the side chain of T114, which can further contribute to the trimer stability. Such close side chain-side chain packing at the interface suggests that lipids are not involved in mediating interactions between monomers

at the points of closest contact. Nevertheless, one cannot rule out a possibility that the fine structure of ASR monomer and trimer could be affected both by the chemistry and phase state of lipids used for reconstitution and by the protein-to-lipid ratios.

The helical arrangement in the TM core of the monomer helical bundle, which contains the retinal-binding pocket, faithfully reproduces the general fold typical for microbial rhodopsins, and is similar to that found in 3D crystals of ASR (**Fig. 4a**).²⁶ This fold is characterized by clustering of helices B, C, F, and G around the retinal Schiff base (**Fig. 4a-b**), typically forming ion-conducting pathways, with helices A, D, and E holding more peripheral positions. While ASR in 3D crystals contains a mixture of *all-trans* and *13-cis* retinal conformers, retinal in the SSNMR structure is found in a single *all-trans* conformation, as can be deduced from single values of chemical shifts detected for the Schiff-base forming Lys210, and C13 and C20 carbons of the retinal. Nevertheless, the conserved residues of the retinal-binding pocket (**Fig. 4b**) and the unique residues of the cytoplasmic polar cluster (**Fig. 4c**) are found in the positions close to those expected from the crystal structure. The retinal (**Fig. 4b**) is flanked by aromatic and polar residues; the latter provide stabilization of the positively charged protonated Schiff base, while the former ensure specificity of retinal photoisomerization. The unique hydrogen-bonded cluster located between the Schiff base and the cytoplasmic surface (**Fig. 4c**) distinguishes ASR from other microbial rhodopsins possessing mainly hydrophobic cytoplasmic halves and is believed to be crucial for the photosensory function. **Figure 4c** shows the location of polar sidechains between helices B, C, and G, which can possibly form a pathway connecting the retinal Schiff base with the cytoplasmic transducer of ASR.

Comparison with the crystal structure of ASR

ASR forms undulating layers of dimers in crystals, with the retinals of two monomers oriented anti-parallel to each other, as viewed from the direction perpendicular to the imaginary lipid bilayer plane (**Fig. 5a**). This observation differs dramatically from the three-fold symmetric organization of trimers in lipids, with each monomer rotated 120° relative to its neighbour (**Fig. 5b**). Such arrangement of the monomers results in the bacteriorhodopsin-like excitonic coupling of the chromophores previously observed using circular dichroism in the visible range.²⁸ In the SSNMR structure, the trimerization is mediated by helix B of one monomer and helices D and E of the neighboring monomer, while the dimers in crystals are stabilized by hydrophobic contacts between the residues in helices D of the two monomers (**Fig. 5a**). This suggests that the crystallization conditions promote the dissociation of trimers, the stabilization of which may be facilitated by lipid-protein interactions. Such alteration of ASR aggregation state by lipids is reminiscent of

bacteriorhodopsin, which changes its oligomerization state from monomeric to trimeric depending on the environment.³⁷

The peripheral interfacial regions differ notably between the SSNMR and X-ray structures. There is a well-defined β -hairpin in the B-C loop on the periplasmic side, which is disordered in the X-ray structure. The β -stranded B-C loops are also observed in the structures of other ASR homologs,^{13, 14, 38} suggesting that this is a characteristic structural feature of the microbial rhodopsin family. The cytoplasmic side, and specifically the cytoplasmic halves of helices A and E in the SSNMR structure deviate largely from those found in the 3D crystals (**Fig. 5c-d**). These two helices are tilted $\sim 10^\circ$ away from the center of the α -helical bundle. Considering that ASR forms stacked undulating layers of dimers in crystals, but tight trimers in lipids, it is not surprising that ASR adopts different local structures in the extramembrane portions and around the oligomerization interfaces. As the vertical contacts between the undulating layers in crystals are mediated by the cytoplasmic loops (such as A-B and E-F),²⁶ these parts may be constrained by the crystal packing but are more mobile in membranes. This is further supported by the site-specific H/D exchange data (**Supplementary Fig. 6**), which show that the deviating ends of helices A and E have a number of exchangeable backbone amides, and are likely mobile.

The X-ray structure of ASR contains internal bound waters, known to bridge several side chain and backbone atoms. Although the location of such waters in the NMR structure is not known, high exchangeability of the interior parts of helices on the cytoplasmic side (**Supplementary Fig. 6**) suggests that internal waters are likely present in the lipid-reconstituted ASR.

DISCUSSION

We determined an atomic resolution structure of a trimeric 7TM membrane protein ASR in lipids, with SSNMR, using a *de novo* (i.e., solved without reliance on a pre-existing template) approach. Our structure determination strategy was conservative in a sense that it relied mainly on the experimental data with minimal use of computational methods and without employing a pre-existing structural template. Our approach combined long-range PRE restraints to determine the oligomeric interface, and internuclear distance restraints and dihedral angle restraints, and experimentally justified intrahelical hydrogen bonds to determine the entire trimer structure. Structure calculation was greatly facilitated by the initial unambiguous assignment of interhelical correlations, and by the straightforward initial identification of the long-range interhelical contacts. With this input information the final interhelical arrangement could

be determined using semi-automated calculations. We showed that the conformation of ASR in lipids has notable differences from that found in crystals.

Our results demonstrate the technical feasibility of structure determination by solid-state NMR for multi-spanning integral membrane proteins. The key question remains as to how general and transferable our approach is to other alpha-helical membrane proteins, specifically eukaryotic ones. The answer, in our opinion, mainly lies in the successful sample preparation. Clearly, ASR possesses properties that facilitate its structure determination. It can be recombinantly expressed in *E. coli* and resides in its inner membrane in the functionally active form. Its transmembrane domain appears to be structurally rigid, while extramembranous loops are relatively short, which gives well-resolved NMR spectra of high signal-to-noise, and facilitates spectroscopic assignments. Its apparent propensity to oligomerize in both detergents and lipids²⁸ allows reaching high protein:lipid ratios in the NMR samples, which translates into higher signal-to-noise ratios of the NMR spectra. ASR samples are stable and show no sign of degradation over long periods of time. While undoubtedly there are membrane proteins, which do not have these properties and would not be amenable to solid-state NMR, there are many other proteins, which are stable in lipids and can yield NMR spectra of similar or higher quality. In particular, our recent study of human Aquaporin 1 reveals spectra of better dispersion and higher resolution than those of ASR.³⁹ In general, solid-state NMR requires large quantities of structurally homogeneous, functional and isotopically labeled membrane protein. While some eukaryotic membrane proteins can be expressed in *E. coli* or produced by cell-free expression,^{14, 40} we have recently demonstrated that high-resolution SSNMR spectra can also be obtained from proteins expressed in yeast,³⁹ which opens an additional avenue for producing functional, isotopically labeled eukaryotic proteins. Neither deuteration nor fast molecular tumbling are required for the successful application of solid-state NMR, which makes it compatible with a broad range of sample preparation conditions, from microcrystals²⁰ to the environment of the lipid bilayer.²¹

A native-like lipid environment is especially attractive because it allows atomic level structural characterization of membrane proteins under nearly physiological conditions, over wide range of temperature and pH, and in various lipid compositions. Importantly, this compatibility makes SSNMR a promising tool for studies of protein-ligand and protein-protein interactions. Furthermore, solid-state NMR offers unique opportunities to study the effects of lipids, both specifically bound and annular ones, on membrane protein structure and dynamics. Although the resolution of solid-state NMR structures is not yet on par with those determined by X-ray crystallography, MAS SSNMR data can be combined with orientational restraints to improve structure quality.^{18, 21} We anticipate that SSNMR will complement

the powerful X-ray crystallography methods, and further facilitate structure determination of large membrane proteins and protein complexes.

Accession codes. Atomic coordinates for the solid state NMR structure and the list of restraints used for structure calculation of ASR have been deposited to the Protein Data Bank under accession code 2m3g.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

S.W., L.S., I.K., and R.A.M. prepared samples; R.A.M. and L.S.B. performed biochemical and FTIR characterization; V.L. and S.W. collected SSNMR data; S.W. processed and analyzed the data, and calculated the structures; T.O. and A.W. synthesized isotopically labeled retinal; S.Y.K. and K.H.J. produced ASR mutants; L.S.B. and V.L. designed the study; S.W., L.S.B. and V.L. wrote the paper. All authors discussed the results of the study.

COMPETING FINANCIAL INTERESTS

The authors declare no competing financial interests.

References

1. Stroud, R.M. New tools in membrane protein determination. *F1000 Biol Rep* **3**, 8 (2011).
2. Bill, R.M. et al. Overcoming barriers to membrane protein structure determination. *Nat Biotechnol* **29**, 335-340 (2011).
3. Palczewski, K. et al. Crystal structure of rhodopsin: A G protein-coupled receptor. *Science* **289**, 739-745 (2000).

4. Cherezov, V. et al. High-resolution crystal structure of an engineered human beta2-adrenergic G protein-coupled receptor. *Science* **318**, 1258-1265 (2007).
5. Rasmussen, S.G. et al. Crystal structure of the human beta2 adrenergic G-protein-coupled receptor. *Nature* **450**, 383-387 (2007).
6. Jaakola, V.P. et al. The 2.6 angstrom crystal structure of a human A2A adenosine receptor bound to an antagonist. *Science* **322**, 1211-1217 (2008).
7. Shimamura, T. et al. Structure of the human histamine H1 receptor complex with doxepin. *Nature* **475**, 65-70 (2011).
8. Kim, H.J., Howell, S.C., Van Horn, W.D., Jeon, Y.H. & Sanders, C.R. Recent Advances in the Application of Solution NMR Spectroscopy to Multi-Span Integral Membrane Proteins. *Prog Nucl Magn Reson Spectrosc* **55**, 335-360 (2009).
9. Hiller, S. & Wagner, G. The role of solution NMR in the structure determinations of VDAC-1 and other membrane proteins. *Curr Opin Struct Biol* **19**, 396-401 (2009).
10. Nietlispach, D. & Gautier, A. Solution NMR studies of polytopic alpha-helical membrane proteins. *Curr Opin Struct Biol* **21**, 497-508 (2011).
11. Zhou, Y. et al. NMR solution structure of the integral membrane enzyme DsbB: functional insights into DsbB-catalyzed disulfide bond formation. *Mol Cell* **31**, 896-908 (2008).
12. Van Horn, W.D. et al. Solution nuclear magnetic resonance structure of membrane-integral diacylglycerol kinase. *Science* **324**, 1726-1729 (2009).
13. Gautier, A., Mott, H.R., Bostock, M.J., Kirkpatrick, J.P. & Nietlispach, D. Structure determination of the seven-helix transmembrane receptor sensory rhodopsin II by solution NMR spectroscopy. *Nat Struct Mol Biol* **17**, 768-774 (2010).
14. Reckel, S. et al. Solution NMR structure of proteorhodopsin. *Angew Chem Int Ed Engl* **50**, 11942-11946 (2011).
15. Berardi, M.J., Shih, W.M., Harrison, S.C. & Chou, J.J. Mitochondrial uncoupling protein 2 structure determined by NMR molecular fragment searching. *Nature* **476**, 109-113 (2011).
16. Lange, A. et al. Toxin-induced conformational changes in a potassium channel revealed by solid-state NMR. *Nature* **440**, 959-962 (2006).
17. Ahuja, S. et al. Helix movement is coupled to displacement of the second extracellular loop in rhodopsin activation. *Nat Struct Mol Biol* **16**, 168-175 (2009).
18. Sharma, M. et al. Insight into the mechanism of the influenza A proton channel from a structure in a lipid bilayer. *Science* **330**, 509-512 (2010).
19. Cady, S.D. et al. Structure of the amantadine binding site of influenza M2 proton channels in lipid bilayers. *Nature* **463**, 689-692 (2010).
20. Shahid, S.A. et al. Membrane-protein structure determination by solid-state NMR spectroscopy of microcrystals. *Nature methods* **9**, 1212-1217 (2012).
21. Park, S.H. et al. Structure of the chemokine receptor CXCR1 in phospholipid bilayers. *Nature* **491**, 779-783 (2012).
22. Manolikas, T., Herrmann, T. & Meier, B.H. Protein structure determination from ¹³C spin-diffusion solid-state NMR spectroscopy. *J Am Chem Soc* **130**, 3959-3966 (2008).
23. Loquet, A. et al. 3D structure determination of the Crh protein from highly ambiguous solid-state NMR restraints. *J Am Chem Soc* **130**, 3579-3589 (2008).
24. Jung, K.H., Trivedi, V.D. & Spudich, J.L. Demonstration of a sensory rhodopsin in eubacteria. *Molecular Microbiology* **47**, 1513-1522 (2003).
25. Wang, S., Kim, S.Y., Jung, K.H., Ladizhansky, V. & Brown, L.S. A eukaryotic-like interaction of soluble cyanobacterial sensory rhodopsin transducer with DNA. *J Mol Biol* **411**, 449-462 (2011).
26. Vogeley, L. et al. Anabaena sensory rhodopsin: a photochromic color sensor at 2.0 Å. *Science* **306**, 1390-1393 (2004).
27. Shi, L., Kawamura, I., Jung, K.H., Brown, L.S. & Ladizhansky, V. Conformation of a seven-helical transmembrane photosensor in the lipid environment. *Angew Chem Int Ed Engl* **50**, 1302-1305 (2011).
28. Wang, S. et al. Paramagnetic relaxation enhancement reveals oligomerization interface of a membrane protein. *J Am Chem Soc* **134**, 16995-16998 (2012).
29. Wang, S., Shi, L., Kawamura, I., Brown, L.S. & Ladizhansky, V. Site-specific solid-state NMR detection of hydrogen-deuterium exchange reveals conformational changes in a 7-helical transmembrane protein. *Biophys J* **101**, L23-25 (2011).
30. Peng, X., Libich, D., Janik, R., Harauz, G. & Ladizhansky, V. Dipolar chemical shift correlation spectroscopy for homonuclear carbon distance measurements in proteins in the solid state: application to structure determination and refinement. *J Am Chem Soc* **130**, 359-369 (2008).
31. Lange, A., Luca, S. & Baldus, M. Structural constraints from proton-mediated rare-spin correlation spectroscopy in rotating solids. *J Am Chem Soc* **124**, 9704-9705 (2002).
32. Castellani, F. et al. Structure of a protein determined by solid-state magic-angle-spinning NMR spectroscopy. *Nature* **420**, 98-102 (2002).
33. Brunger, A.T. et al. Crystallography & NMR system: A new software suite for macromolecular structure determination. *Acta crystallographica* **54**, 905-921 (1998).
34. Bardiaux, B., Malliavin, T. & Nilges, M. ARIA for solution and solid-state NMR. *Methods in molecular biology (Clifton, N.J)* **831**, 453-483 (2012).

35. Nadaud, P.S., Helmus, J.J., Hofer, N. & Jaroniec, C.P. Long-range structural restraints in spin-labeled proteins probed by solid-state nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy. *J Am Chem Soc* **129**, 7502-7503 (2007).
36. Essen, L., Siegert, R., Lehmann, W.D. & Oesterhelt, D. Lipid patches in membrane protein oligomers: crystal structure of the bacteriorhodopsin-lipid complex. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* **95**, 11673-11678 (1998).
37. Dencher, N.A. & Heyn, M.P. Formation and properties of bacteriorhodopsin monomers in the non-ionic detergents octyl-beta-D-glucoside and Triton X-100. *Febs Lett* **96**, 322-326 (1978).
38. Shi, L. et al. Three-Dimensional Solid-State NMR Study of a Seven-Helical Integral Membrane Proton Pump—Structural Insights. *J Mol Biol* **386**, 1078-1093 (2009).
39. Emami, S., Fan, Y., Munro, R., Ladizhansky, V. & Brown, L.S. Yeast-expressed human membrane protein aquaporin-1 yields excellent resolution of solid-state MAS NMR spectra. *J Biomol NMR* **55**, 147-155 (2013).
40. Klammt, C. et al. Facile backbone structure determination of human membrane proteins by NMR spectroscopy. *Nature methods* **9**, 834-839 (2012).

Figure Legends

Figure 1. Solid-state NMR spectra of ASR recorded on sparsely labeled samples. Cross-peaks corresponding to intra-helical restraints ($1 < |i-j| \leq 5$) and restraints within the loops connecting adjacent helices (excluding the β -stranded B-C loop) are labeled in blue. Red labels denote inter-helical correlations, and correlations defining the short β -hairpin within the B-C loop. **(a)** Part of the 2D PDSD spectrum collected with mixing time of 500 ms on 1,3-ASR containing correlations between C ζ atoms of tyrosines or arginines with aliphatic sidechains. **(b)** Part of the 2D 500 ms PDSD spectrum of 2-ASR containing C α -C α correlations or correlations of C α and C δ of proline residues. **(c)** Region of CHHC spectrum of 1,3-ASR containing methyl-methyl correlations. **(d)** Representative 2D N-CX plane [$F_1 - F_3$] of the HBR² spectrum of 1,3-ASR at the carbonyl chemical shift of 178.2 ppm.

Figure 2. Schematic representation of iterative long-range cross-peak assignment and convergence of structure calculation. **(a,c,e)** Helical wheel representations of ASR monomer viewed from the periplasmic side. Unambiguous long-range contacts identified in SSNMR spectra and used in steps 1 **(a)**, 2 **(c)** and 3 **(e)** of the structure calculations are depicted by red lines connecting the correlated residues. Dashed red lines connect two residues having at least one unambiguous distance restraint between them. Blue bar represents retinal and blue solid lines represent restraints between the retinal and the residues on helix C (T80 and L83) and helix F (Y179). Blue solid lines represent the intra-monomer PRE restraints. **(b,d,f)** Ensembles of 10 lowest energy structures (out of 100) obtained as described in the step 1 **(b)**, 2 **(d)** and 3 **(f)** of the structure calculation protocol. Retinal is yellow. RMSDs are calculated for backbone atoms of α -helices.

Figure 3. Overall topology and inter-monomer packing of ASR trimer. **(a-b)** A comparison of inter-monomer interfaces of ASR **(a)** and BR (pdb code 1BRR) **(b)**. View from the periplasmic side is on the left. Monomers are colored differently. Boxed regions highlight the interfaces. Inter-monomer side chain packing is shown on the right. Inter-monomer contacts detected in the 2D PDSD spectra of ASR are shown by dashed lines. **(c)** Sequence alignment of ASR and BR for residues in helices B, D and E showing similarities in the amino acid positions and differences in the chemical makeup of the oligomerization interfaces. Residues involved in the inter-monomer contacts are shown in red.

Figure 4. Structural organization of ASR monomer. **(a)** Side view of SSNMR monomer structure extracted from the lowest-energy trimer structure. Retinal is orange, cytoplasmic side is on top. **(b)** Sidechains of selected residues

forming the retinal-binding pocket are shown in light green. (c) A polar pocket formed by residues in the cytoplasmic halves of helices B, C, and G viewed from the cytoplasmic side.

Figure 5. A comparison of ASR structures in 3D crystals and in lipids. (a-b) ASR structure in crystals (pdb code 1XIO) (a) and in lipids (b), viewed from the periplasmic side. Monomers are shown in different colors with α -helices represented by cylinders. Retinals are represented by sticks. Black arrows indicate the orientation of retinal chromophores, pointing from the Schiff base to the β -ionone ring. Enlarged boxed region of (a) highlights the side chain packing on the intermonomer interface of the crystal structure of ASR. (c-d) Comparison of the protein backbone of the crystal structure of ASR (grey) with that of a monomer structure extracted from an ASR trimer (red) viewed from the cytoplasmic (c) and periplasmic (d) sides.

Online Methods

Expression and Purification of ASR. C-terminally truncated (at the position 229) 6-histidine-tagged version of ASR was expressed in BL21-Codonplus-RIL *E. coli* cells following the previously described protocol.²⁷ Sparsely ¹³C-labeled ASR samples for internuclear distance measurements were grown in M9 minimal media containing ¹⁵N-labeled ammonium chloride, and [1,3-¹³C] glycerol or [2-¹³C] glycerol (all isotopes purchased from Cambridge Isotope Laboratories). Retinal labeled at positions 13 and 20 was added exogenously at a concentration of 7.5 μ M to regenerate the expressed opsin. Cells were broken by sonication and the membrane fraction was solubilized in 1 % DDM. The protein was purified following the batch protocol as described in the Qiagen Ni²⁺-NTA manual (Qiagen). The purified protein solubilized in 0.05% DDM was reconstituted into DMPC/DMPA liposomes (9:1 w/w) by detergent removal using Bio-beads SM-2 (Bio-Rad). The protein to lipid ratio was 2:1 (w/w), as confirmed by transmission Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy⁴¹ (**Supplementary Fig. 7**).

NMR Spectroscopy. Approximately 8 mg of 1,3-ASR or 2-ASR sample were transferred and center-packed in a thin wall 3.2 mm rotor. PDS and CHHC NMR experiments were performed at 5°C (sample temperature) on a 800 MHz Bruker Avance III spectrometer (Bruker Biospin Ltd). 3D HBR² measurements were performed on a 600 MHz Bruker Avance III spectrometer. Both spectrometers were equipped with Bruker E-free ¹H-¹³C-¹⁵N 3.2 mm probes.

Experimental details and parameters of NMR experiments are described in **Supplementary Table 1**. Carbon and nitrogen chemical shifts were indirectly referenced with respect to 2,2-dimethyl-2-silapentane-5-sulfonic acid (DSS) by adjusting the position of the ¹³C adamantane downfield peak to 40.48 ppm.⁴² Homogeneously broadened rotational resonance width experiments (HBR²)^{30, 43} for distance measurements were recorded on a 600 MHz spectrometer at a MAS frequency of 11.2 kHz using the standard NCOCX pulse sequence with the HBR² mixing time of 70 ms. CW proton decoupling during mixing was adjusted to approximately 45 kHz to efficiently recouple dipolar interactions between the ¹³C carbonyl spins ($\sim 175 \pm 10$ ppm) and the ¹³C labeled aliphatic side chain atoms (mainly methyl and some methylene groups) through $n = 2$ matching condition. Additional experimental parameters are given in **Supplementary Table 1**. NMR data were processed using NMRpipe⁴⁴ and analyzed using CARRA⁴⁵. The previously reported ¹⁵N and ¹³C chemical shift assignments of the ASR (BMRB code: 18595) were used for data analysis.⁴⁶

Structural restraints. Backbone dihedral angles were derived from TALOS+⁴⁷ using N, C', C α and C β chemical shifts (**Supplementary Fig. 4**). Only angles defined as “good” by TALOS+ were used as dihedral restraints with margins of errors set to double values given by the program. The upper limit of distance HBR² restraints was set to 5.5 Å. Carbon-carbon restraints derived from the PDS experiments with mixing times of 100, 250, and 500 ms were

used with the upper bounds of 5.5, 6.5, and 7.5 Å, respectively. ^1H - ^1H distance restraints determined from CHHC spectra were defined with the upper bound of 5.0 Å. On the basis of the knowledge of well-defined secondary structure elements, the intra-helical H-bonds restraints were introduced, defined as distances between oxygen O_i and proton H_{i+4} , set to 1.8-2.5 Å, if both chemical shift index and TALOS+ indicated helical structures for both residues, and NMR restraints involving $\text{C}\alpha$ - $\text{C}\alpha_{i+3}$, $\text{C}\alpha$ - $\text{C}\beta_{i+3}$, $\text{H}\alpha$ - $\text{H}\alpha_{i+3}$, $\text{H}\alpha$ - $\text{H}\beta_{i+3}$, C' - $\text{C}\alpha_{i+3}$ and/or C' - $\text{C}\beta_{i+3}$ pairs were detected.

Electron-nuclear distance restraints were derived from the Paramagnetic Relaxation Enhancement (PRE) effects characterized on a uniformly ^{15}N , ^{13}C -labeled S26C mutant of ASR. The details of sample preparations and data analysis were reported previously.²⁸ Strong PRE's (with relative intensities smaller than 0.33 compared to the diamagnetic reference) were converted into electron-nuclear restraints with the upper bound of 15 Å. For atoms not affected by the nitroxide radical (with relative intensities larger than 0.70 compared to the diamagnetic reference), the distance restraints were set with the lower bound of 23 Å.

Structure Determination. ASR trimer structure was calculated through a semi-automated structure calculation protocol described below. **Structure Calculation Protocol.** The program CNS (Crystallography and NMR system, version 1.21)³³ was used to generate the structures through a simulated annealing protocol. ARIA program (version 2.3)³⁴ was used to disambiguate the long-range cross peaks. The retinal coordinates were included by introducing a modified residue at the position of Lys210. The force field parameters and topology of retinal and modified lysine were adopted from the theoretical calculation based on bacteriorhodopsin structure.⁴⁸⁻⁵¹ The conformer of retinal was defined as all-*trans* and 15-*anti* on the basis of ^{15}N chemical shift of the nitrogen atom of the Schiff base and carbon shifts of Lys210 (ref. 27) and chemical shifts of C13 and C20 retinal carbons,⁴⁶ which were consistent with those reported for all-*trans*, 15-*anti* retinal.^{52,53} To include PRE restraints, S26 was replaced by cysteine with attached nitroxide radical,²⁸ with the side chain parameters adopted from ref. 54.

Structure Calculation Protocol. Step 1: Generating template structure of monomeric ASR. The initial *de novo* template was obtained with a set of unambiguous distance restraints derived from the analysis of 2D and 3D spectra. We first categorized the cross peaks into three groups: (i) short-range peaks that correspond to either intra-residue or sequential correlations; (ii) medium-range peaks that can be interpreted as originating from residues conforming to $1 < |i-j| < 5$ and can not be explained by short-range interactions; (iii) long-range peaks that can not be classified into group (i) or (ii). In the initial structure calculations, the short- and medium range peaks were not considered. Two monomer structure calculations were carried out. In the first, the cross peaks that could be interpreted as inter-helical restraints between helices A or B of one monomer, and helices D or E of another monomer were temporarily excluded,

because these helices were previously shown to form the trimerization interface.²⁸ In the second, all restraints were considered as discussed at the end of **Step 3** below.

11 long-range peaks from group (iii) could be assigned based on the chemical shifts and using the knowledge of labeling patterns of proteins grown on alternately labeled glycerols^{32,55} (**Fig. 2a and Supplementary Table 2**). Additional 24 cross peaks were disambiguated by considering the basic properties of the transmembrane helices, the boundaries of which can be found from the chemical shift analysis, giving us the topological map of ASR. Namely, residues on the opposite sides of the protein (i.e., cytoplasmic vs. periplasmic) can not give rise to spin-spin correlations because they are too far from each other. Additionally, residues in the cytoplasmic and periplasmic regions can not give correlations to carbon atoms C13 and C20 of the retinal, because both C13 and C20 are close to the Schiff base, and are located in the middle of the bilayer. The location of the retinal could be independently obtained from the NMR data showing correlation of the Schiff base nitrogen to lysine-210 sidechain carbons.

The template was calculated using CNS program from a total of 32 *non-redundant* restraints (**Fig. 2a and Supplementary Table 2**), combined with dihedral angle restraints (186 ϕ, ψ pairs) obtained from TALOS+ program,⁴⁷ intra-helical H-bonds restraints (defined as distances between oxygen O_i and proton H_{i+4} , set to 1.8-2.5 Å) introduced based on TALOS+, and 24 intra-monomer PRE restraints.²⁸ The short- and medium- range restraints derived from the cross peaks of group (i) and (ii) were temporarily excluded. An ensemble of 10 structures selected from the 100 calculated was obtained with RMSD of 3.2 Å for backbone atoms of α -helices (**Fig. 2b**).

Step 2: Automated Assignments of Ambiguous Restraints Using ARIA. The manually obtained structure ensemble in step 1 was used as the template to further resolve the ambiguity of long-range peaks, using the standard iterative protocol implemented in ARIA 2.3 program.³⁴ Typical ¹³C line widths observed in the spectra of ASR were 0.2-0.5 ppm, about two times narrower than those observed in protein samples with uniform ¹³C labeling,²² justifying setting the chemical shift tolerance window in structure calculation to 0.1 ppm. An upper distance bound was set to 10 Å for assigned restraints, considering that the initial template has low backbone and side chain resolution. Violation tolerance of the first iteration was set to 5 Å, and the number of iterations was set to six. Manual inspection of assigned contacts was performed at the end of this round, and the assignments involving side chains of residues separated by two helical turns, or of residues pointing in the opposite directions of adjacent helical turns (*i* to *i*+6 contacts) were discarded. A total of 79 long-range unambiguous restraints were obtained at the end of this round, resulting in an ensemble of ten lowest energy structures with a reduced RMSD of helical regions of 1.3 Å (**Fig. 2c-d**).

Step 3: Second Round of ARIA Assignments. The family of ten lowest energy structures obtained in step 2 was

subjected to another round of iterative assignment and structure calculation. All other input parameters were the same as in step 2, with the exception of the violation tolerance of the first iteration, which was set to 3 Å, and of the upper distance bound of restraints, reduced to 7.5 Å. With the template of higher precision, additional 100 unambiguous long-range constraints were identified, bringing the total count of assigned long-range cross peaks to 211, and reducing the helical backbone RMSD to 0.9 Å (**Fig. 2e-f**).

In Step 1 above we used the knowledge of the oligomeric interface, which was derived from the analysis of PRE patterns²⁸ using the X-ray structure of ASR. To verify if the oligomeric interface can be determined from PREs without the use of X-ray data, we carried an additional structure calculation following steps 1-3, but this time without including the intramolecular PREs constraining relative orientations of helices A and B, and without excluding the potential contacts between helices A and B of one monomer, and helices D or E of another monomer. The resulting structure was similar to the one shown in **Figure 2f** (relative RMSD 2.2 Å), and could be used in lieu of the X-ray structure for the interpretation of the PREs and for building the oligomeric interface.

Step 4: High-Resolution Monomer ASR Structure Calculated Using Assigned Restraints. The cross peaks of group (i) and (ii) define the local structures, and were assigned manually according to local geometry and the geometry of secondary structure elements, e.g., intra-helical contacts were expected to be detected between residue *i* and residue *i+3* or *i+4*.⁵⁶ The final high-resolution monomer structures were calculated using the unambiguous short- and medium-range restraints, unambiguous long-range restraints obtained by manual interpretation or ARIA calculations, dihedral angle restraints,

and intra-monomer PRE restraints (**Supplementary Tables 2-4**). Additionally, H-bonds were defined as distances between oxygen O_i and proton H_{i+4} , set to 1.8-2.5 Å if both chemical shift index and TALOS+ indicated helical structures for both residues, and NMR restraints involving Ca-Ca_{i+3} , $\text{Ca-C}\beta_{i+3}$, $\text{Ha-H}\alpha_{i+3}$, $\text{Ha-H}\beta_{i+3}$, $\text{C}'\text{-Ca}_{i+3}$ and/or $\text{C}'\text{-C}\beta_{i+3}$ pairs were detected. An ensemble of 10 structures out of 100 structures was finally obtained with an RMSD of helical regions of 0.6 Å (**Supplementary Fig. 5**).

Step 5: Identification of additional intermonomer internuclear constraints in 2D NMR spectra. PRE measurements performed on a uniformly ¹⁵N,¹³C labeled S26C ASR and presented by us earlier²⁸ identified that the intermonomer interface is comprised by helices A and B and helices D and E of two adjacent monomers. We assumed the trimeric arrangement of ASR based on the evidence previously presented in ref. 28): 1) SDS-PAGE shows the existence of trimers in detergent (Supplementary figure S4 in ref. 28); 2) chemical cross-linking experiments indicate trimers both in detergent and DMPC/DMPGA lipids (Supplementary figures S5A, S5B in ref. 28); 3) Circular Dichroism

in the visible range conducted on the solubilized and lipid-reconstituted ASR show that the oligomerization states are equivalent in both environments (figure S6 in ref. 28). The inter-monomer PRE effects were converted into inter-monomer distance restraints and along with the monomer structure of step 4 used to generate a trimer template, using rigid body docking program HADDOCK.^{57,58} An average of the 10 lowest-energy trimer structures (out of 100) was used to identify the inter-monomer contacts in 2D PDS spectra. Cross peaks that could not be assigned to intramonomer contacts were subjected to analysis. In agreement with PRE data, all identified inter-monomer contacts were between helices B and D (F42C β -S107C β and W46C ϵ 2-T114C α), and helices B and E (I56C δ 2-V127C γ 1, I56C δ 2-V127C γ 2, L49C α -W131C ϵ 3, and M52C ϵ -C134C β) (**Fig. 3a**). These restraints were used to calculate a structure of the full trimer.

Step 6: Full Trimer Structure. The final round of structure calculation used unambiguous intra- and inter- monomer distance restraints derived from NMR spectra, dihedral angle restraints, intrahelical H bonds as defined in **Step 4**, and PRE restraints (**Supplementary Table 5**). C3 symmetry was set to minimize the structural variation between the monomer units, as ASR forms symmetric trimers, as confirmed by the absence of multiple peaks for the same nuclei.²⁸ 100 randomized initial trimer structures were generated from three copies of a randomized monomer structures, and subjected to CNS³³ structure calculation using a three-stage simulated annealing protocol: high temperature sampling at 10,000K (10,000 steps), an annealing stage from 20,000 K to 1000 K (144,000 steps), and final annealing stage from 1000 K to 50 K (144,000 steps). An ensemble of 10 lowest energy conformers was selected with RMSD of 0.8 Å for backbone atoms of α -helices. The lowest energy structure is shown in **Figure 3a**. The coordinates of nitroxide labels were removed and the modified cysteine at the position 26 was changed back to native serine prior to structure quality evaluation using PROCHECK,⁵⁹ WHAT IF^{60,61} (online server: <http://swift.cmbi.ru.nl/servers/html/index.html>) and MolProbity⁶² (online server: <http://molprobity.biochem.duke.edu/>). The structures have been deposited into the Protein Data Bank (PDB ID code 2m3g).

References

41. daCosta, C.J. & Baenziger, J.E. A rapid method for assessing lipid:protein and detergent:protein ratios in membrane-protein crystallization. *Acta crystallographica* **59**, 77-83 (2003).

42. Morcombe, C.R. & Zilm, K.W. Chemical shift referencing in MAS solid state NMR. *J Magn Reson* **162**, 479-486 (2003).
43. Janik, R., Peng, X. & Ladizhansky, V. (13)C-(13)C distance measurements in U-(13)C, (15)N-labeled peptides using rotational resonance width experiment with a homogeneously broadened matching condition. *J Magn Reson* **188**, 129-140 (2007).
44. Delaglio, F. et al. Nmrpipe - a Multidimensional Spectral Processing System Based on Unix Pipes. *J Biomol NMR* **6**, 277-293 (1995).
45. Keller, R. The Computer Aided Resonance Assignment Tutorial Edn. first. (CANTINA Verlag Goldau 2004).
46. Wang, S. et al. Solid-state NMR (13)C and (15)N resonance assignments of a seven-transmembrane helical protein Anabaena Sensory Rhodopsin. *Biomol NMR Assign* **in press**, DOI: 10.1007/s12104-12012-19421-y (2012).
47. Shen, Y., Delaglio, F., Cornilescu, G. & Bax, A. TALOS+: a hybrid method for predicting protein backbone torsion angles from NMR chemical shifts. *J Biomol NMR* **44**, 213-223 (2009).
48. Tajkhorshid, E., Paizs, B. & Suhai, S. Conformational effects on the proton affinity of the Schiff base in bacteriorhodopsin: A density functional study. *J Phys Chem B* **101**, 8021-8028 (1997).
49. Tajkhorshid, E., Baudry, J., Schulten, K. & Suhai, S. Molecular dynamics study of the nature and origin of retinal's twisted structure in bacteriorhodopsin. *Biophys J* **78**, 683-693 (2000).
50. Tajkhorshid, E. & Suhai, S. Influence of the methyl groups on the structure, charge distribution, and proton affinity of the retinal Schiff base. *J Phys Chem B* **103**, 5581-5590 (1999).
51. Baudry, J., Crouzy, S., Roux, B. & Smith, J.C. Quantum chemical and free energy simulation analysis of retinal conformational energetics. *J Chem Inf Comp Sci* **37**, 1018-1024 (1997).
52. Farrar, M.R. et al. Solid-State Nmr-Study of [Epsilon-C-13]Lys-Bacteriorhodospin - Schiff-Base Photoisomerization. *Biophys J* **65**, 310-315 (1993).
53. Smith, S.O. et al. Structure and Protein Environment of the Retinal Chromophore in Light-Adapted and Dark-Adapted Bacteriorhodopsin Studied by Solid-State NMR. *Biochemistry-US* **28**, 8897-8904 (1989).
54. Sammalkorpi, M. & Lazaridis, T. Modeling a spin-labeled fusion peptide in a membrane: implications for the interpretation of EPR experiments. *Biophys J* **92**, 10-22 (2007).
55. Higman, V.A. et al. Assigning large proteins in the solid state: a MAS NMR resonance assignment strategy using selectively and extensively 13C-labelled proteins. *J Biomol Nmr* **44**, 245-260 (2009).
56. Zech, S.G., Wand, A.J. & McDermott, A.E. Protein structure determination by high-resolution solid-state NMR spectroscopy: Application to microcrystalline ubiquitin. *J Am Chem Soc* **127**, 8618-8626 (2005).
57. Dominguez, C., Boelens, R. & Bonvin, A.M. HADDOCK: a protein-protein docking approach based on biochemical or biophysical information. *J Am Chem Soc* **125**, 1731-1737 (2003).
58. de Vries, S.J. et al. HADDOCK versus HADDOCK: new features and performance of HADDOCK2.0 on the CAPRI targets. *Proteins* **69**, 726-733 (2007).
59. Laskowski, R.A., Macarthur, M.W., Moss, D.S. & Thornton, J.M. Procheck - a Program to Check the Stereochemical Quality of Protein Structures. *J Appl Crystallogr* **26**, 283-291 (1993).
60. Vriend, G. WHAT IF: a molecular modeling and drug design program. *Journal of molecular graphics* **8**, 52-56, 29 (1990).
61. Rodriguez, R., Chinea, G., Lopez, N., Pons, T. & Vriend, G. Homology modeling, model and software evaluation: three related resources. *Bioinformatics* **14**, 523-528 (1998).
62. Chen, V.B. et al. MolProbity: all-atom structure validation for macromolecular crystallography. *Acta crystallographica* **66**, 12-21 (2010).

Figure-1 (Ladizhansky)

Figure-2 (Ladizhansky)

Figure-3 (Ladizhansky)

c

Helix B: ASR: Y L V A M ⁴⁰ F I P I W S G L ⁵⁰ A Y M A M A I
 BR: Y A I T T L V P A I A F T M Y L S M L L
 50 60

Helix D: ASR: L I G F L M ¹⁰¹ S T Q I V V I T S G L I A D ¹²⁰
 BR: T I L A L V G A D G I M I G T G L V G A
 110 120

Helix E: ASR: W V R Y L ¹³⁰ W Y I C G V C A F L I I L W G I ¹⁴⁰
 BR: S Y R F V W W A I S T A A M L Y I L Y V L
 140 150

Figure-4 (Ladizhansky)

Figure-5 (Ladizhansky)

